

Classical Potential $V(x)$ as an Entangled State and Positive and Negative Energy Regions in Space?

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The concept of free particle energy arises from special relativity, i.e. $m_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$. In the nonrelativistic limit this becomes $m_0 c^2 + p^2/2m_0$. We have argued that free particle quantum mechanics, $\exp(ipx) \exp(-iEt)$ also arises from special relativity due to degeneracy in the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et + px$ with t and x . Extending this to probabilities yields $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$.

If one considers $\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx)$, then one has an entangled state because p and $-p$ do not exist at sharp times and places, but rather there is a resolution, \hbar/p and \hbar/E . There must, however, be something creating this p and $-p$ entangled state because a momentum p does not suddenly change into $-p$. This suggests the presence of a force which changes p to $-p$ and vice versa at some boundaries. In other words, one may consider an infinite well potential. We consider that even though there is a $p = \text{constant}$ in the region with no potential, there are still all of the $\exp(ipx)$ s present and they represent an entangled state: $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ such that a p may change into a different p_2 with kinetic energy lost if $p_2 < p$ or gained if $p_2 > p$. In other words, in general p leads to the creation of kinetic energy in some cases, and the loss of it in other cases. We suggest that in equilibrium this leads to negative and positive kinetic energy regions linked with $\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx)$ which are of the size of \hbar/p . I.e. the resolution size. In other words, constant kinetic energy in x is linked with gains and losses of free particle kinetic energy (from $\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx)$) in successive half wavelength regions. We then extend this idea to the case of a $V(x)$ in all of space.

We suggest that $V(x)$ also represents an entangled state, but one which may stand alone in space (if it is not interacting with any particle). Thus, if one writes $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$, one cannot have k momentum move to infinite. In other words, V_k represents a basic energy linked with k and one does not think of k as having a kinetic energy as well. k , however, can deliver an impulse hit to a free particle and in doing so change p_1 to $p_1 + k$. In this case, the intrinsic energy of V_k is still present, but now kinetic energy is created if k is positive, or it is lost if k is negative (in 1-D). As a result, if one has a single particle interacting with $V(x)$, it should become entangled with the already entangled $V(x)$. If one considers the $\exp(ipx)$ term, then one has: $\sum_k V_k a(p-k) \exp(ipx)$ where $a(p-k)$ is a weight for $\exp(i(p-k)x)$. What does this entanglement entail in terms of energy? The fact that one has a kinetic energy of $p^2/2m$ for every k to $p-k$ combination means that one expects a term of $a(p) p^2/2m \exp(ipx)$. The intrinsic energy V_k associated with $\exp(ikx)$, however, does not disappear, and comes into play, but only with the product probability $a(p-k)$ in order that one has an overall momentum of p . Thus, one has $a(p) p^2/2m \exp(ipx) + \sum_k V_k a(p-k) \exp(ipx)$, but the first term contains all of the created kinetic energies by k interacting with $p-k$. For equilibrium, one has the same overall energy everywhere, so these two terms add to $E a(p) \exp(ipx)$. The question then becomes: If a k momentum from the potential, linked with energy V_k , changes the kinetic energy of a particle with $p-k$, then it seems that energy is not conserved. If there were no particle, then there would be energy V_k (linked to k from the potential). Now there is $\sum_k V_k a(p-k)$ and $p^2/2m a(p)$. Just as in the infinite well potential case, however, one has $\exp(ipx)$ regions such that adding an equation for $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$, one has positive and negative kinetic energy regions

showing that kinetic energy may be lost to the potential as well as gained. In other words, one does not always have an increase in kinetic energy along with V_k .

In other words, the idea of positive and negative kinetic energy regions for constant p ($\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx)$) allows one to have conservation of energy in space.

Quantum Free Particles and the Notion of Entanglement

We have argued in previous notes that free particle quantum mechanics arises from the degeneracy of the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et + px$ for:

$$x = x_0 + n \cdot \hbar/p \quad ((1a)) \quad \text{and} \quad t = t_0 + n \cdot \hbar/E \quad ((1b)) \quad \text{where } n \text{ is an integer}$$

This in turn leads to complex probabilities $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ such that there is conservation of energy and momentum, e.g. $P_1(p_1x)P_1(p_2x) = P_1((p_1+p_2)x)$. ((2))

The point we wish to make is that there is uncertainty in x and t and so one cannot consider precise E, p states at each (x, t) as in classical mechanics. Rather, one must consider an entangled state:

$$W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx) \quad (\text{for } t \text{ removed}) \quad ((3))$$

In such a case, one may consider entangled energy:

$$KE_{ave}(x) = \{ \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) p^2/2m \exp(ipx) \} / W(x) \quad ((4))$$

In other words, one may consider conservation of energy at each x point only for averages because the uncertainty in x and t does for a constant p, E does not allow for conservation at a x point (if t is removed).

We next suggest that if this is the case, then the classical potential $V(x)$ should also represent entangled energy as well. The issue with the potential, however, is that one cannot have constituents with k move to \pm infinite. In other words, if one writes:

$$V(x) = \text{Sum over } k \ V_k \exp(ikx) \quad ((5))$$

Then one considers an energy V_k which is not associated with kinetic energy, while k can impart an impulse on a particle and change its p to $p+k$, thus creating kinetic energy. Thus, we suggest that $W(x)$ should become entangled with $V(x)$, namely:

$$V(x)W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ \{ \text{Sum over } k \ V_k \ a(p-k) \} \exp(ipx) \quad ((6))$$

Now one must try to interpret the energy because V_k remains while $p-k$ (particle) \rightarrow p particle gains kinetic energy. In other words, $V(x)$ seems to be creating kinetic energy without losing any of its values V_k . The issue, we argue, is considering what happens on average over x .

To try to understand what is happening, we consider the case of an infinite well potential.

Infinite Well Potential

An infinite well potential has no potential values within $[-L, L]$. Thus, one would expect an average energy $p^2/2m$ in this region. That does not mean that there is no entanglement. There is still the result:

$$\exp(ipx) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((7))$$

This suggests that p values are changing into each other even in a place with no potential energy, but overall average energy must be conserved. This seems to suggest that a given $\exp(ipx) a(p)$ may contribute $p^2/2m$ in some region and then remove it from another. This cannot occur at a point x because of the resolution \hbar/p . These regions should be of the same length and we argue should correspond to $.5 \hbar/p$, i.e. a half wavelength. For an equilibrium scenario, one would expect one half wavelength to add $p^2/2m$ and then next to remove it. This must occur so that:

$$\left\{ \sum_p a(p) p^2/2m (\exp(-ipx) + \exp(ipx)) \right\} / W(x) = p^2/2m \quad ((8)) \quad \text{for } a(p) = a(-p)$$

Nevertheless, one sees the pattern of $\cos(px)$, i.e. a negative $p^2/2m \cos(px)$ in one half wavelength followed by $-p^2/2m |\cos(px)|$ in the next half wavelength. This ensures an average constant energy. We argue that this same kind of scenario should exist for the case of $V(x)$.

$V(x)$ and Negative and Positive Kinetic Energy Regions

We argued in the section before the previous that $V(x)$ is an entangled state which becomes further entangled with $W(x)$. This leads to V_k energy pieces being retained as well as kinetic energy being created when k from the potential combines with $p-k$ from a particle. At first, this suggests a loss of conservation of energy. In other words, one has two pieces for a given $\exp(ipx)$:

$$\sum_k V_k a(p-k) \quad ((9a)) \quad \text{and} \quad a(p) p^2/2m \quad ((9b))$$

We argue that $p^2/2m a(p)$ in $((9b))$ come from the kinetic energy produced by all terms in the entangled $((9a))$ term. There is again, however, positive and negative kinetic energy regions if $a(p) = a(-p)$ and one considers a sum of coefficients for $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$. This situation of positive and negative kinetic energy terms in different spatial regions, together with $V_k a(-p-k)$ and $V_k a(p-k)$ terms allows one to have average conservation among changes of average $KE(x)$ with $V(x)$. This conservation, however, occurs on average. Thus, to only consider $V_k a(p-k)$ and $p-k \rightarrow p$ is misleading in that it gives the sense of extra energy always being created, i.e. nothing diminishes V_k . It is $V(x)$ which may be diminished.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we suggest that $V(x)$ represents a special entangled state for which the energy is V_k for each k . Thus, one does not consider a separate kinetic energy for k , but notes that it may give an impulse hit to a particle $p-k$ creating p . In such a case, kinetic energy is created, but V_k is retained giving the sense of an overall creation of energy, i.e. no conservation. We suggest, however, that if one examines an infinite well potential, then average kinetic energy is constant, and one has $\exp(ipx)$ as a wavefunction, but this is equivalent to $\sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$. In other words, if one considers $a(p)=a(-p)$, then $a(p)\cos(px)$ terms contribute positive and negative kinetic energy in alternating half wavelength regions and it is this behaviour we argue which allows for constant kinetic energy on average.

We suggest that this idea carries over to the case with a potential $V(x)$. In such a case, one has an entangled state $V(x)$ which becomes further entangled with $W(x)$. This leads to energy terms $V_k a(p-k)$, but also to extra kinetic energy as $p-k$ becomes k . This energy appears in $a(p) p^2/2m$ for the factor $\exp(ipx)$. Conservation of energy at each x on average is possible, however, because considering $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ with $a(p)=a(-p)$ again allows for the addition and removal of kinetic energy from alternating half wavelength regions (resolution regions) and similar considerations even apply to $V_k a(p-k)$ and $V_k a(-p-k)$ so that overall one is able to create $KE_{ave}(x)+V(x)=E$, i.e. average conservation of energy in space.

In short, in quantum mechanics one has resolution units in space of \hbar/p and so one can only add or remove kinetic energy on average for a constant p in these regions, not at a point x as in classical physics. It is only the average kinetic energy + $V(x)$ which may be conserved at a point x .